

Predictive modelling of osteoporosis and effect of BMI on the risk of fracture in femur bone using COMSOL Multiphysics: a computational modelling approach

Aleena Kamal¹, Minahil Kamal¹, Mashal Fatima¹, Syed Muddusir Hussain¹,
Jawwad Sami Ur Rahman¹, Sathish Kumar Selvaperumal²

¹Department of Biomedical Engineering, Riphah International University, Islamabad, Pakistan

²Faculty of Engineering, Asia Pacific University of Technology and Innovation, Kuala Lumpur, Malaysia

Article Info

Article history:

Received May 7, 2024

Revised Nov 30, 2024

Accepted Feb 27, 2025

Keywords:

Body mass index

Bone health

COMSOL Multiphysics

Fracture risk

Osteoporosis

ABSTRACT

This study explores the intricate relationship between osteoporosis, body mass index (BMI), and the risk of femur fractures using computational modeling. Osteoporosis is a silent metabolic disorder that depletes bone density and structure, significantly increasing the risk of fractures, particularly in weight-bearing bones such as the femur. To analyze the impact of mechanical stress on osteoporotic bones, COMSOL Multiphysics was utilized to simulate stress distribution in a femur under varying BMI conditions, providing valuable insights into how BMI influences bone health and fracture risk. A three-dimensional (3D) femur model was designed using computer-aided design (CAD) software, with specific material properties assigned for both healthy and osteoporotic bones. Finite element analysis was conducted by applying different load conditions, representing body weight, on the femur head. The results highlighted stress distribution and deformation patterns, identifying regions most prone to fracture. The findings demonstrate that while higher BMI typically correlates with increased bone density, it also leads to greater deformation in osteoporotic bones under stress, emphasizing the complex interplay between BMI and bone strength. These insights underscore BMI's critical role in fracture risk management. Future research should incorporate advanced fracture mechanics models and clinical data to enhance predictive accuracy and develop targeted strategies for fracture prevention in osteoporotic patients.

This is an open access article under the [CC BY-SA](#) license.

Corresponding Author:

Sathish Kumar Selvaperumal

Faculty of Engineering, Asia Pacific University of Technology and Innovation

57000, Kuala Lumpur, Malaysia

Email: sathish@apu.edu.my

1. INTRODUCTION

Roughly 15% of the adult human body weight comprises bone, a thick, stiff connective structure made of cells, collagen fibers, and minerals, primarily calcium and phosphate [1], [2]. The 206 bones comprising the axial and appendicular skeletons comprise the human body [3], [4]. The production of blood cells by bone marrow, support and protection of vital organs, and mobility are just a few of the many important roles that bones perform [5], [6]. Of all these vital roles, forming the human body's structural skeleton is the most significant.

Bone diseases encompass a spectrum of problems that may impact the strength, structural soundness, and general state of the bone. Numerous variables, such as age, gender, hormonal imbalance,

dietary inadequacies, changes in lifestyle, genetic anomalies, can cause these illnesses [7]. Bone cancer, rheumatoid arthritis, osteoporosis, and osteoarthritis are a few of the most frequent bone illnesses [8], [9]. Pain, fractures, deformities, and a host of other issues can result from these disorders and compromise one's quality of life. Early diagnosis of bone problems can be greatly aided by diagnostic methods such as bone density evaluation, medical imaging, and blood testing [10], [11].

One of the most prevalent metabolic bone diseases, osteoporosis causes bone tissue to deteriorate and lose mass [12], [13]. This raises the possibility of fractures by making the bone brittle. Since osteoporosis does not manifest any signs until the bone fractures or cracks, it is known as a silent illness [14]. According to research, 200 million people globally may be affected by osteoporosis. Hip fractures are predicted to affect half of Asia's population by 2050, which is causing growing worry in the region [15].

Osteoporosis has several reasons, one of which is aging. As people age, their natural bone density gradually declines, which causes their bones to become fragile [16], [17]. Furthermore, because menopause speeds up bone loss, women are more likely than males to acquire osteoporosis [18], [19]. In addition, a person's family history and lifestyle decisions may increase their chance of getting osteoporosis. Osteoporosis can also result from excessive alcohol use, smoking, and nutritional deficits that compromise bone health [20]–[22]. Among those over fifty, one in three women and one in five men suffer from osteoporosis-related fractures [23]. The bone becomes weak and porous enough to break with little strain or stress when osteoporosis weakens and reduces the density of the bone. This may provide a risk to those with osteoporosis [24]. Weight-bearing bones like the femur (thigh bone), and tibia (shinbone), are susceptible to stress fractures [25].

The body mass index, or BMI, is a popular statistic for determining a person's body weight in proportion to their height [26], [27]. Reduced bone density and structural degeneration of bone tissue, on the other hand, are characteristics of osteoporosis [28]. The relationship between osteoporosis and BMI, as well as the risk of fractures, is nuanced and multifaceted [29].

The impact of body weight on bone density is one factor in the connection between osteoporosis and BMI. In general, bone mineral density is higher in those with higher BMIs. Increased body weight puts more mechanical stress on bones, which can promote bone remodeling and increase bone mass. Because of this, those with higher BMIs could be somewhat protected from osteoporosis [30].

The link is not, however, exclusively based on total BMI. One important factor is how body fat is distributed. Increased BMI is frequently linked to excess belly fat, which may be detrimental to bone health [31]. An imbalance in the molecules that adipose tissue generates can affect bone metabolism and potentially lead to a reduction in bone density [32], [33].

The interaction of several variables also affects the association between fracture risk and BMI. Because of their greater bone density, those with higher BMIs may be somewhat more resistant to fractures, but bone tissue quality is just as vital. In certain situations, people with higher BMIs may still be at risk for fractures if there is a structural defect in their bones, such as poor bone quality or certain medical disorders [34].

The longest and strongest bone in the human body is the femur, sometimes referred to as the thigh bone. It is a weight-bearing bone that contributes to shock absorption by allowing the leg to move freely and shield surrounding tissues and joints from severe impact. Additionally, it is a significant location for the attachment of several vital muscles that support stable leg movement [35], [36]. Figure 1 depicts the anatomical structure of the femur.

Figure 1. Anatomical structure of femur in human

An increasing number of older people, particularly those with osteoporosis, suffer fractures in the proximal femur, which is situated close to the hip joint. These fractures fall into two main categories: femoral neck fractures, which involve the femur's neck, and intertrochanteric fractures, which happen between the greater and lesser trochanters [37]. Surgical intervention is frequently necessary for proximal femur fractures to accurately realign and stabilize the fragmented bone pieces, promote efficient healing, and restore functional abilities.

An excessive build-up of body fat, or obesity, introduces a complicated interaction of variables that affect the risk of fracture in osteoporotic femur bones. Obesity, ironically, is linked to negative impacts on bone quality and bone metabolism, even if larger body mass can have some protective benefits on bone density through increased mechanical stress [38]. Obese people's increased weight on weight-bearing bones, including the femur, may cause changes in bone structure, such as an increase in bone mineral density. However, this seeming benefit is offset by the negative consequences of obesity-related conditions, such as persistent inflammation and hormone abnormalities, which worsen the damaged bone microenvironment. Furthermore, the way body fat is distributed, especially visceral fat, might result in the production of inflammatory chemicals that could harm bone health [39].

The biomechanical effects of obesity also need to be taken into account. Being overweight can put the femur under increased mechanical stress, which may be more than the bone's regenerative ability, particularly in those who already have osteoporosis. An increased incidence of femur fractures may result from this increased mechanical strain as well as the poorer bone quality linked to fat. Because of this, the relationship between obesity and the risk of fracture for osteoporotic femurs is complex, having a mix of favorable and unfavorable effects on bone health. To enhance bone health and reduce the incidence of femur fractures, it is imperative to comprehend this complexity to create tailored therapies that meet the unique problems given by obesity in persons with osteoporosis.

Despite previous research highlighting the association between osteoporosis, BMI, and fracture risk, current computational models lack precise predictions of fracture locations in osteoporotic femurs under varying BMI conditions. Prior research shows that higher BMI is often associated with increased bone density due to mechanical stress; however, excessive adiposity and fat distribution may adversely impact bone quality. This study aims to bridge this gap by utilizing COMSOL Multiphysics to model the femur bone under mechanical stress, providing detailed insights into how BMI influences fracture risk. The study's goal is to better understand the relationship between bone health, BMI, and osteoporosis, focusing on identifying high-stress regions in the femur susceptible to fracture.

This paper builds on existing works by integrating computational modelling with clinical observations to predict the risk of fracture in osteoporotic femurs. The findings are expected to aid in the development of tailored treatments and preventative measures for individuals at risk of osteoporosis-related fractures. The paper is structured as follows: first, the methodology is described in detail, followed by the presentation of simulation results, which are then discussed in relation to current research. The conclusion summarizes key findings and suggests directions for future research.

2. METHOD

The primary objective of this study is to assess the fracture risk in osteoporotic femur bones by simulating mechanical stress using COMSOL Multiphysics. COMSOL Multiphysics was chosen for its capacity to model the complex mechanical behavior of bones under stress and to simulate fracture risks accurately. The model's integration of material properties such as young's modulus and poisson's ratio allows for realistic simulation of osteoporotic conditions. This computational approach predicts stress distribution in the femur under various load conditions, focusing on the influence of BMI on bone strength. The model provides a detailed understanding of how external forces contribute to bone deformation and potential fracture sites in osteoporotic individuals.

2.1. Geometric design

The study began with the creation of a two-dimensional (2D) femur model, which was converted to a 3D representation through volume rendering in COMSOL Multiphysics. The femur geometry was imported into the software shown in Figure 2, and all necessary parameters, such as bone dimensions and mechanical properties, were added to accurately simulate an osteoporotic bone.

2.2. Material properties

The material properties of both healthy and osteoporotic bones were applied. A healthy bone has a young's modulus of 16.5 GPa, a poisson's ratio of 0.43, and a density of 2,000 kg/m³ as shown in Table 1. However, osteoporotic bones, characterized by a decrease in rigidity, were assigned different properties

shown in Table 2. These differences were incorporated into the entire femur geometry to accurately reflect the reduced strength and increased porosity of osteoporotic bones as shown in Figure 3.

Figure 2. A 3D model of the femur in COMSOL Multiphysics

Table 1. Material properties of a healthy bone

Properties	Value	Units
Young's modulus	16.5	GPa
Poison's ratio	0.43	1
Density	2,000	Kg/m ³

Table 2. Material properties of an osteoporotic bone

Properties	Value	Units
Young's modulus	11.5	GPa
Poison's ratio	0.2	1
Density	800	Kg/m ³

Figure 3. Material applied to entire geometry

2.3. Physics type

The "Solid mechanics" physics module was utilized to analyze stress distribution and structural integrity under mechanical loading. This module is crucial for understanding deformation and failure points in bones subjected to high stress. Using this physics, the model simulates the impact of different force magnitudes on the femur, incorporating tools for fracture mechanics and damage accumulation.

2.4. Meshing

To enhance the simulation's accuracy, the femur geometry was meshed into smaller finite elements, allowing for detailed analysis of stress and deformation patterns. An extra-coarse mesh was applied for computational efficiency while maintaining adequate resolution. This meshing allowed us to strike a balance between accuracy and the computational cost of the simulation. The mesh of the geometry is shown in Figure 4.

Figure 4. Extra coarse mesh applied to femur geometry

2.5. Applying the load

The femur bone which is also known as the thigh bone, is located in the upper portion of the leg. It connects the hip joint to the knee joint. The proximal end of the femur is attached to the hip joint while the distal end is attached to the knee joint. The femur is a critical load-bearing bone that facilitates movement and supports body weight.

The femur is subjected to mechanical forces associated with body weight. As the body weight increases, the magnitude of load on the femur's head increases which can impact its stress distributions. Osteoporosis is a disorder that makes the bones porous and brittle and they become more sensitive to load-bearing activities. Therefore, people having a BMI value greater than 30 are considered to be obese and are more likely to develop osteoporosis. Their bones are subject to higher mechanical loading due to their weight.

A normal femur bone can adhere to a weight equal to 30 times the normal body weight but an osteoporotic bone can bear lesser weight and is more likely to crack or have increased fracture risk. A static load of approximately 2,000 N was applied to the head of the femur, simulating the effects of body weight on the hip joint shown in shown in Figure 5, where Figure 5(a) illustrates the applied boundary load on the femur head and Figure 5(b) shows the fixed distal end of the femur. The distal end of the femur was fixed to prevent articulation, ensuring that any deformation and stress occurred solely due to the applied load.

Figure 5. Boundary conditions of the femur model (a) boundary load of ~2000 N applied at the femur head to simulate body weight and (b) the distal end of the femur is fixed to prevent movement and ensure stress develops solely from the applied load

This boundary condition enabled the observation of stress distributions and potential fracture sites in osteoporotic femurs under different load magnitudes. The effect of BMI on fracture risk was also analyzed by simulating various body weights, showing how increased load on the osteoporotic femur increases the risk of fracture shown in Figure 6. The force applied to the femur is influenced by body weight, intensity of physical activities performed as well and any external forces acting on it. The load is considered a static load and the inclination angle is 0 degrees. The femur being a strong bone is designed in a way that it can withstand forces associated with various activities like walking, running, and jumping.

An osteoporotic femur becomes brittle enough that it can deform easily once it is subjected to load and the risks of fracture are much greater as compared to normal bone. Therefore, people suffering from Osteoporosis need to keep an eye on their BMI. People having more than normal body weight are more susceptible to developing fractures in their bones.

Figure 6. Forces are applied to the head of the femur

2.6. Finite element analysis

For the structural analysis of the osteoporotic femur and to analyze its behavior when it is subjected to load, it is divided into finite elements. The stress was applied on the head of the femur and the displacement is shown in Figure 7. The most stressed area can be shown in red color which is the head while the proximal end has the least stress which is shown in blue color. In this analysis, a range of loads were applied to the head of the femur, and maximum stress sites were observed. These sites are at an elevated risk of developing fractures in the future.

Figure 7. Finite element analysis

2.7. Deformation and maximum stress site

The deformation of the femur bone when approximately 200 kg of load is applied is shown in Figure 8. Specifically, Figure 8(a) illustrates the deformation under load, while Figure 8(b) highlights the resulting stress concentration. When the load is applied to the femur’s head, the maximum stress is observed in the shaft which is shown by the red color in the shaft of the bone as shown in Figure 8(b). This shows that the shaft of the femur is more prone to developing cracks when load is applied.

As depicted in Figure 9, a contour plot was generated to visualize stress distribution across the femur. Red areas indicate high stress, primarily concentrated at the femur’s head and shaft, while blue areas represent regions of lower stress. These findings suggest that the femur’s shaft is particularly vulnerable to fractures when exposed to excessive loads, especially in individuals with reduced bone density.

Figure 8. Finite element results of femur under static loading (a) deformation observed when 2,000 N is applied to the femur head and (b) stress concentration visualized primarily along the femoral shaft

Figure 9. Contour plot

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

When an external force is applied to an osteoporotic femur, the resulting deformation patterns are critical in determining high-risk areas for fracture. Our simulations revealed that under a load of approximately 2,000 N, the femur exhibits significant deformation in the shaft region, which corresponds to the highest stress concentration. This result aligns with clinical observations of fractures typically occurring in this region among osteoporotic patients.

When force is applied to an osteoporotic femur, the deformation is noticeable. This information shows areas that are subjected to higher strain. The deformation magnitude can help determine the risk of fracture in the future. The difference is visible when forces between 1,000 N (approximately 100 kg) to 2,000 N (approximately 200 kg) are applied as shown in are applied as shown in Figure 10, which includes subfigures 10(a), 10(b), and 10(c) corresponding to deformation under 100 kg, 150 kg, and 200 kg loads, respectively.

It is quite clear from the findings that when an osteoporotic femur is subjected to increasing force, we observe a corresponding increase in its deformation, primarily manifesting as bending. This is where things start to get interesting but also worrying: there is a tipping point at which the bone can no longer bear the strain, depending on its density, strength, and mineral content. Contrary to the assumption that higher BMI protects against osteoporosis, the simulation demonstrated that increased weight leads to a higher risk of fractures due to localized stress in specific bone regions. Depending on the general health of the bone, this threshold changes from one to the next.

Interestingly, when forces were gradually increased from 1,000 N to 2,000 N, the deformation magnitude showed a linear relationship with the applied force as shown in Figure 11. This indicates that osteoporotic femurs, though less dense, still follow predictable mechanical behavior patterns under stress. However, the threshold at which these bones fracture is significantly lower compared to healthy bones.

The results contrast with studies that suggest higher BMI offers some protection against fractures due to increased bone mass. The findings, however, highlight the counterproductive effects of high BMI when paired with osteoporosis. Although elevated BMI may increase bone density, the mechanical stress from additional body weight exacerbates fracture risk due to compromised bone quality in osteoporotic individuals.

Figure 10. Deformation of the femur under varying static loads: (a) under 100 kg load, minor displacement is observed mostly in the femur head, (b) under 150 kg load, moderate deformation extends to the shaft, and (c) under 200 kg load, significant stress is distributed along the shaft and femur head, indicating higher risk of structural failure

Figure 11. Linear relationship between force and stress

4. CONCLUSION

The study used COMSOL Multiphysics to simulate the effects of BMI on osteoporotic femur strength and fracture risk. The results emphasize the importance of considering BMI in fracture risk assessments, particularly in patients with osteoporosis. While higher BMI can increase bone density, it also leads to stress concentrations that may increase fracture risk. Future studies should integrate advanced fracture mechanics to improve the model’s predictive capabilities. Collaborations with clinicians to validate the model’s accuracy through clinical data would enhance its practical applicability. Incorporating imaging techniques like computed tomography (CT) scans could refine the bone’s geometrical representation, further improving fracture risk prediction.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

The authors, with regard to the consent taken, sincerely acknowledge the valuable insights and guidance provided by Engr. Touseef Yaqoob from the Intelligent Systems Research Lab, United Kingdom, throughout the development of this research. His expertise and constructive feedback greatly contributed to refining the conceptual framework and technical aspects of this study. We are grateful for his continuous support and encouragement, which played a pivotal role in enhancing the quality of this work.

FUNDING INFORMATION

Authors state no funding involved.

AUTHOR CONTRIBUTIONS STATEMENT

Name of Author	C	M	So	Va	Fo	I	R	D	O	E	Vi	Su	P	Fu
Aleena Kamal	✓		✓	✓				✓	✓				✓	
Minahil Kamal		✓						✓	✓		✓	✓		
Mashal Fatima	✓		✓	✓					✓		✓		✓	
Syed Muddusir Hussain					✓		✓			✓		✓		✓
Jawwad Sami Ur Rahman						✓				✓				
Sathish Kumar					✓					✓				
Selvaperumal										✓				

C : Conceptualization
 M : Methodology
 So : Software
 Va : Validation
 Fo : Formal analysis

I : Investigation
 R : Resources
 D : Data Curation
 O : Writing - Original Draft
 E : Writing - Review & Editing

Vi : Visualization
 Su : Supervision
 P : Project administration
 Fu : Funding acquisition

CONFLICT OF INTEREST STATEMENT

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper. Authors state no conflict of interest.

DATA AVAILABILITY

The data that support the findings of this study are available from the corresponding author, Sathish Kumar Selvaperumal, upon reasonable request.

REFERENCES

- [1] A. Öchsner and W. Ahmed, *Biomechanics of hard tissues: modeling, testing, and materials*. Wiley, 2010.
- [2] D. B. Burr, "Bone morphology and organization," in *Basic and Applied Bone Biology*, Elsevier, 2019, pp. 3–26.
- [3] M. Caon, "Skeletal system," in *Examination Questions and Answers in Basic Anatomy and Physiology*, Springer International Publishing, 2020, pp. 185–212.
- [4] B. W. Anderson, J. Ekblad, A. C. Black, and B. Bordoni, "Anatomy, appendicular skeleton," in *StatPearls*, StatPearls Publishing LLC, 2024.
- [5] N. Su *et al.*, "Bone function, dysfunction and its role in diseases including critical illness," *International Journal of Biological Sciences*, vol. 15, no. 4, pp. 776–787, 2019, doi: 10.7150/ijbs.27063.
- [6] E. C. Watson and R. H. Adams, "Biology of bone: the vasculature of the skeletal system," *Cold Spring Harbor Perspectives in Medicine*, vol. 8, no. 7, p. a031559, Sep. 2018, doi: 10.1101/cshperspect.a031559.
- [7] A. Costantini *et al.*, "Early-onset osteoporosis: rare monogenic forms elucidate the complexity of disease pathogenesis beyond type i collagen," *Journal of Bone and Mineral Research*, vol. 37, no. 9, pp. 1623–1641, 2022, doi: 10.1002/jbmr.4668.
- [8] G. Adami and K. G. Saag, "Osteoporosis pathophysiology, epidemiology, and screening in rheumatoid arthritis," *Current Rheumatology Reports*, vol. 21, no. 7, p. 34, Jul. 2019, doi: 10.1007/s11926-019-0836-7.
- [9] C. S. Thudium *et al.*, "Bone phenotypes in rheumatology – there is more to bone than just bone," *BMC Musculoskeletal Disorders*, vol. 21, no. 1, p. 789, Dec. 2020, doi: 10.1186/s12891-020-03804-2.
- [10] A. S. Areeckal, M. Kocher, and S. D. S., "Current and emerging diagnostic imaging-based techniques for assessment of osteoporosis and fracture risk," *IEEE Reviews in Biomedical Engineering*, vol. 12, pp. 254–268, 2019, doi: 10.1109/RBME.2018.2852620.
- [11] S. Hussain *et al.*, "Modern diagnostic imaging technique applications and risk factors in the medical field: a review," *BioMed Research International*, vol. 2022, no. 1, Jan. 2022, doi: 10.1155/2022/5164970.
- [12] M. M. Sobh *et al.*, "Secondary osteoporosis and metabolic bone diseases," *Journal of Clinical Medicine*, vol. 11, no. 9, p. 2382, Apr. 2022, doi: 10.3390/jcm11092382.
- [13] B. C. Lupsa and K. Insogna, "Bone health and osteoporosis," *Endocrinology and Metabolism Clinics of North America*, vol. 44, no. 3, pp. 517–530, Sep. 2015, doi: 10.1016/j.ecl.2015.05.002.
- [14] H. M. Moutsopoulos and E. Zampeli, "Bone, cartilage, and soft tissue disorders," in *Immunology and Rheumatology in Questions*, Cham: Springer International Publishing, 2021, pp. 175–187.
- [15] P. Pisani *et al.*, "Major osteoporotic fragility fractures: risk factor updates and societal impact," *World Journal of Orthopedics*, vol. 7, no. 3, pp. 171–181, 2016, doi: 10.5312/wjo.v7.i3.171.
- [16] T. A. Hillier *et al.*, "WHO absolute fracture risk models (FRAX): Do clinical risk factors improve fracture prediction in older women without osteoporosis?," *Journal of Bone and Mineral Research*, vol. 26, no. 8, pp. 1774–1782, Feb. 2011, doi: 10.1002/jbmr.372.
- [17] C. J. Rosen, *The epidemiology and pathogenesis of osteoporosis*. South Dartmouth (MA): MDText.com, Inc., 2015.
- [18] X. Zheng, S. K. Lee, and O. K. Chun, "Soy Isoflavones and osteoporotic bone loss: a review with an emphasis on modulation of bone remodeling," *Journal of Medicinal Food*, vol. 19, no. 1, pp. 1–14, Jan. 2016, doi: 10.1089/jmf.2015.0045.
- [19] V. Bandela, B. Munagapati, R. K. R. Karnati, G. R. S. Venkata, and S. R. Nidudhur, "Osteoporosis: its prosthodontic considerations – a review," *Journal of Clinical and Diagnostic Research*, vol. 9, no. 12, pp. ZE01–ZE04, 2015, doi: 10.7860/JCDR/2015/14275.6874.
- [20] R. Bijelic, S. Milicevic, and J. Balaban, "The influence of non-preventable risk factors on the development of osteoporosis in postmenopausal women," *Materia Socio-Medica*, vol. 31, no. 1, pp. 62–65, 2019, doi: 10.5455/msm.2019.31.62-65.
- [21] A. L. Jensen, G. Wind, B. L. Langdahl, and K. Lomborg, "The impact of multifaceted osteoporosis group education on patients' decision-making regarding treatment options and lifestyle changes," *Journal of Osteoporosis*, vol. 2018, pp. 1–10, 2018, doi: 10.1155/2018/9703602.
- [22] S. Rozenberg *et al.*, "How to manage osteoporosis before the age of 50," *Maturitas*, vol. 138, pp. 14–25, Aug. 2020, doi: 10.1016/j.maturitas.2020.05.004.
- [23] M. Lorentzon *et al.*, "Osteoporosis and fractures in women: the burden of disease," *Climacteric*, vol. 25, no. 1, pp. 4–10, Jan. 2022, doi: 10.1080/13697137.2021.1951206.
- [24] M. S. LeBoff *et al.*, "The clinician's guide to prevention and treatment of osteoporosis," *Osteoporosis International*, vol. 33, no. 10, pp. 2049–2102, Apr. 2022, doi: 10.1007/s00198-021-05900-y.
- [25] M. A. Kumbhalkar, K. S. Rambhad, and N. Jee Kanu, "An insight into biomechanical study for replacement of knee joint," in *Materials Today: Proceedings*, 2021, vol. 47, pp. 2957–2965, doi: 10.1016/j.matpr.2021.05.202.
- [26] F. Q. Nuttall, "Body mass index: obesity, BMI, and health: a critical review," *Nutrition Today*, vol. 50, no. 3, pp. 117–128, May 2015, doi: 10.1097/NT.0000000000000092.
- [27] S. Chung, "Body mass index and body composition scaling to height in children and adolescent," *Annals of Pediatric Endocrinology & Metabolism*, vol. 20, no. 3, p. 125, 2015, doi: 10.6065/apem.2015.20.3.125.
- [28] M. Lorentzon and S. R. Cummings, "Osteoporosis: the evolution of a diagnosis," *Journal of Internal Medicine*, vol. 277, no. 6, pp. 650–661, May 2015, doi: 10.1111/joim.12369.
- [29] K. Hu *et al.*, "Understanding the consequences of fatty bone and fatty muscle: how the osteosarcopenic adiposity phenotype uncovers the deterioration of body composition," *Metabolites*, vol. 13, no. 10, p. 1056, Oct. 2023, doi: 10.3390/metabo13101056.
- [30] N. K. Pollock, "Childhood obesity, bone development, and cardiometabolic risk factors," *Molecular and Cellular Endocrinology*, vol. 410, pp. 52–63, Jul. 2015, doi: 10.1016/j.mce.2015.03.016.
- [31] C. Savvidis, S. Tournis, and A. D. Dede, "Obesity and bone metabolism," *Hormones*, vol. 17, no. 2, pp. 205–217, Jun. 2018, doi: 10.1007/s42000-018-0018-4.
- [32] J. Li, X. Chen, L. Lu, and X. Yu, "The relationship between bone marrow adipose tissue and bone metabolism in postmenopausal osteoporosis," *Cytokine and Growth Factor Reviews*, vol. 52, pp. 88–98, Apr. 2020, doi: 10.1016/j.cytogfr.2020.02.003.

- [33] S. Muruganandan, R. Govindarajan, and C. J. Sinal, "Bone marrow adipose tissue and skeletal health," *Current Osteoporosis Reports*, vol. 16, no. 4, pp. 434–442, May 2018, doi: 10.1007/s11914-018-0451-y.
- [34] A. Palermo *et al.*, "BMI and BMD: the potential interplay between obesity and bone fragility," *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, vol. 13, no. 6, p. 544, May 2016, doi: 10.3390/ijerph13060544.
- [35] K. S. Zakiuddin, I. A. Khan, and R. A. Hinge, "A review paper on biomechanical analysis of human femur," *International Journal of Innovative Research in Science and Engineering*, vol. 2, no. 03, pp. 356–363, 2016.
- [36] A. Chang, G. Breeland, A. C. Black, and J. B. Hubbard, *Anatomy, bony pelvis and lower limb, femur*. Treasure Island (FL): StatPearls Publishing, 2023.
- [37] S. E. Sheehan, J. Y. Shyu, M. J. Weaver, A. D. Sodickson, and B. Khurana, "Proximal femoral fractures: what the orthopedic surgeon wants to know," *Radiographics*, vol. 35, no. 5, pp. 1563–1584, Sep. 2015, doi: 10.1148/rg.2015140301.
- [38] P. JafariNasabian, J. E. Inglis, O. J. Kelly, and J. Z. Ilich, "Osteosarcopenic obesity in women: Impact, prevalence, and management challenges," *International Journal of Women's Health*, vol. 9, pp. 33–42, Jan. 2017, doi: 10.2147/IJWH.S106107.
- [39] A. P. Frank, R. De Souza Santos, B. F. Palmer, and D. J. Clegg, "Determinants of body fat distribution in humans may provide insight about obesity-related health risks," *Journal of Lipid Research*, vol. 60, no. 10, pp. 1710–1719, Oct. 2019, doi: 10.1194/jlr.R086975.

BIOGRAPHIES OF AUTHORS

Aleena Kamal is a final-year student of biomedical engineering at Riphah International University, Islamabad, holding a CGPA of 3.81 out of 4.00 across 120 out of 135 credit hours. With a fervent passion for research, Aleena's interests lie predominantly in biomedical signal processing, medical imaging, medical image processing, instrumentation, and artificial intelligence. She has an experience in internship at the Combined Military Hospital, Rawalpindi. She consistently contributes positively to both her academic studies and extracurricular activities. Formerly serving as the Chairperson of IEEE Women in Engineering, Riphah Students Branch, she has been honored with the prestigious Best WIE AG award. She is currently serving as the Graphics Lead for the IEEE PES/PELS Joint Chapter, IEEE Islamabad Section. Additionally, her academic excellence has earned her the esteemed Rise Pride of Performance Award. She effectively utilizes her strong critical thinking, time management, and communication skills to contribute meaningfully to her academic and extracurricular endeavors. She can be contacted at email: aleenakamal25@gmail.com.

Minahil Kamal is a dedicated biomedical engineering student at Riphah International University, Islamabad, who showcases an exemplary academic record with a perfect CGPA of 4.00/4.00 over 87/135 credit hours. She is passionate about the convergence of engineering and life sciences and is committed to innovation and has an experience of internship in the domain of biomedical engineering at the Combined Military Hospital, Rawalpindi. Her research interests include biomedical instrumentation, microprocessors and interfacing techniques, digital logic design, medical robotics, bio signal processing, artificial intelligence, machine learning, deep learning, and embedded systems. She has been recognized with the prestigious Silver Medal for securing the 2nd position in presenting her research work at the IEEE Symposium 2024. She has also been awarded the prestigious Rise Pride of Performance Award for her academic record. Beyond academia, she actively engages in research, project development, and content writing, and has proficiency in various software languages. She holds top positions in co-curricular and extra-curricular competitions and is also an active member of the IEEE Riphah Students Branch, EMBS, and WIE-IEEE. She is currently serving as the Marketing and Promotion Lead for the IEEE PES/PELS Joint Chapter, IEEE Islamabad Section. She has excellent communication, writing, and critical-thinking skills, and has received honorary awards in biomedical engineering, solidifying her as a standout professional in the making. She can be contacted at email: 35377@students.riphah.edu.

Engr. Mashal Fatima Ph.D. scholar is currently working as Sr. Lecturer at Riphah International University after graduating from the same university as a biomedical engineer in 2014 (receiving gold medal) and completing masters in 2016 (gold medalist). Her area of research includes signal processing, bio modeling, robotics, and its interfacing with bio-signals. She is also working on signal processing of different bio-signals, especially EEG feature extraction for diagnostic and therapeutic causes. She can be contacted at email: mashal.fatima@riphah.edu.pk.

Engr. Syed Muddusir Hussain is a notable figure in biomedical engineering, with numerous achievements in academia and industry. Holding a Bachelor's and Master's degree in biomedical engineering from Sir Syed University of Engineering and Technology, he excelled in innovation and problem-solving. Currently pursuing a Ph.D. at Riphah International University, he also serves as a lecturer, renowned for his engaging teaching and mentorship. His expertise encompasses medical device design, with impactful research in computational modeling, medical electronics, and healthcare technology. He has authored and supervised numerous papers, both nationally and internationally, and actively participates in industry events, showcasing his leadership and collaboration. His commitment to innovation and continuous learning makes him a valuable asset to the biomedical engineering community, contributing significantly to advancements in patient care and industry knowledge. He can be contacted at email: muddasir.hussain@riphah.edu.pk.

Dr. Jawwad Sami Ur Rahman has done BS in biomedical engineering in 2011 from Sir Syed University of Engineering & Technology from Pakistan & an M.Sc. in technology management in 2013 and done Ph.D. in engineering from Asia Pacific University in 2023. His research interest revolves around the analysis of brain tumors by applying various medical image segmentation techniques in MRI images. Currently, he is working as an assistant professor at Riphah International University in Islamabad, Pakistan. Moreover, he is the branch counselor of IEEE for the Faculty of Engineering and Applied Sciences (FEAS) and Co-Chairman of the MDT Board in Pakistan for tumor research. He can be contacted at email: Jawwad.sami@riphah.edu.pk.

Dr. Sathish Kumar Selvaperumal completed his Ph.D. program at Sri Chandrasekharendra Saraswathi Viswa Mahavidyalaya University, Chennai, India in the year 2014. He completed his B.E degree in electronics and communication engineering in the year 2001 and his M.E applied electronics in the year 2006, at Arulmigu Meenakshi Amman College of Engineering, Kanchipuram, Chennai, India. He has 20 years of teaching experience and he is currently working as an associate professor and program leader for Telecommunication Engineering at Asia Pacific University (APU) of Technology and Innovation, Technology Park of Malaysia, Kuala Lumpur, Malaysia. He is the final year project manager at the School of Engineering, APU. He is a chartered engineer (CEng, UK) and a member of the Institution of Engineering and Technology (IET), Institute of Electrical and Electronics Engineers (IEEE), Indian Society for Technical Education (ISTE), International Association of Computer and Information Technology (IACIST), Singapore and International Association of Engineers (IAENG), Hong Kong. He has been the reviewer for more than 50 international conferences and journals. He has published and presented more than 50 research papers at national and international conferences and reputed journals. He has been the keynote speaker for various international conferences. His research interests are image segmentation in angiogram images, brain and liver images, image enhancement, image compression, image retrieval, watermarking and speech detection and speech processing, optical communication, IoT, antenna design, artificial intelligence, and robotics. He can be contacted at email: sathish@apu.edu.my.